

SR. NO.

SCHOOL INFORMATION SCHEDULE

INSTRUCTIONS

THIS SCHOOL INFORMATION SCHEDULE IS TRYING TO COLLECT INFORMATIONS FROM YOUR SCHOOL ABOUT STUDENT ENROLMENT, RETENTION, SCHOOL PARTICULARS, AND SCHOOL FACILITIES ETC. YOU ARE REQUESTED TO PROVIDE ACTUAL INFORMATION. THE INFORMATION GIVEN BY YOU WILL REMAIN CONFIDENTIAL AND WILL BE USED FOR RESEARCH PURPOSES ONLY. WE ARE GRATEFUL TO YOU FOR YOUR SUPPORT.

THANKING YOU!

PROF. P. K. JOSHI
RESEARCH SUPERVISOR

AMBIKA BHATT
(RESEARCH SCHOLAR)

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
SCHOOL OF EDUCATION, BIRLA CAMPUS
H. N. B. GARHWAL UNIVERSITY, SRINAGAR GARHWAL

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1. NAME OF SCHOOL _____ | 2. NAME OF BLOCK _____ |
| 3. NAME OF DISTRICT _____ | 4. YEAR OF ESTABLISHMENT _____ |
| 5. SCHOOL CATEGORY (PRIMARY =1, UPPER PRIMARY =2, PRIMARY + UPPER PRIMARY =3) <input type="checkbox"/> | 6. ADDRESS OF SCHOOL _____ |
| 7. TYPE OF SCHOOL (BOYS =1, GIRLS =2, CO-EDU.=3) <input type="checkbox"/> | 8. NAME OF PRINCIPAL /HEADMASTER _____ |
| 9. LOCALE OF SCHOOL(RURAL =1, URBAN =2) <input type="checkbox"/> | 10. NO. OF TEACHERS IN SCHOOL _____ |
| 11. MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL(GOVT. =1/ PVT. =2) <input type="checkbox"/> | 12. NO. OF STUDENTS IN SCHOOL _____ |

ITEM. NO.	A. ACCESS TO THE SCHOOL	
1.	DISTANCE FROM MAIN ROAD (IN KM.) _____	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	DISTANCE FROM DISTRICT HEADQUARTER (IN KM.) _____	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	DISTANCE FROM BLOCK HEADQUARTER (IN KM.) _____	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	ACCESS OF SCOOOL (SUGAM =1, DURGAM =2, ATI DURGAM =3)	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	ROUTE TO SCHOOL IS FOR ALL WEATHER(YES =1, NO =2)	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	VILLAGES COVERED _____	<input type="checkbox"/>

ITEM NO.	B. SCHOOL PARTICULARS	
1.	NAME OF SCHOOL _____	
2.	LOCALITY OF SCHOOL (RURAL =1, URBAN =2)	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	NAME OF BLOCK _____	
4.	DISTANCE OF SCHOOL (IN KM.) 1. FROM BLOCK HEADQUARTER _____ <input type="checkbox"/> 2. FROM DISTRICT HEAD QUARTER _____ <input type="checkbox"/>	
5.	YEAR OF ESTABLISHMENT _____ <input type="text"/>	
6.	SCHOOL TYPE (1= BOYS, 2= GIRLS, 3 =CO-EDU.)	<input type="checkbox"/>
7.	SCHOOL MANAGEMENT (1 =GOVT., 2 =PVT.)	<input type="checkbox"/>

10.	BLACK BOARD	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
11.	CHALK AND DUSTER	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
12.	MAPS	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
13.	SCIENCE LAB	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
14.	HISTORY CHART /ALPHABET CHARTS /COUNTING CHARTS	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15.	TELEPHONE	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
16.	FIRE EXTINGUISHER	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
17.	SPORTS EQUIPMENT	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
18.	CULTURAL EQUIPMENT	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
19.	ELECTRICITY (yes =1, no =2, available but not functioning =3) <input type="checkbox"/>		
20.	AVAILABILITY OF COMPUTER (yes =1, no =2, available but not functioning =3) <input type="checkbox"/>		
21.	TOTAL NO. OF CLASSROOMS IN SCHOOLS 1. primary level _____ <input type="checkbox"/> 2. upper primary level _____ <input type="checkbox"/>		
22.	NO. OF SANCTIONED POSTS OF TEACHERS _____ <input type="checkbox"/>		
23.	NO. OF WORKING TEACHER _____ <input type="checkbox"/>		
24.	OWNERSHIP OF SCHOOL BUILDING(1 =own, 2 =rental, 3 =govt., 4 =other) 1. own 2. rental 3. Govt. 4. other <input type="checkbox"/>		
25.	TYPE OF SCHOOL BUILDING(1 =pacca, 2 =kachha, 3 =mixed, 4 =other, 5 =no building) 1. pacca 2. kachha 3. mixed 4. other 5. no building <input type="checkbox"/>		

26.	CONDITION OF BUILDING(1 =no repair, 2 =minor repair, 3 =major repair, 4 =dilapidated) 1. no repair 2. minor repair 3. major 4. Dilapidated	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									
27.	PROVISION OF DRINKING WATER(1 =tap water, 2 =streams, 3 =spring, 4 =well, 5 =hand pump, 6 =none, 7 =any other) 1. tap water 2. streams 3. Spring 4. well 5. hand pump 6. none 7. any other(specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									
28.	AVAILABILITY OF FURNITURE FOR TEACHERS(1 =available to all, 2 =available to some, 3 =available to none) 1. available to all 2. available to some 3. available to none	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									
29.	AVAILABILITY OF FURNITURE FOR STUDENTS(1 =available to all, 2 =available to some, 3 =available to none) 1. available to all 2. available to some 3. available to none	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									
30.	AVAILABILITY OF OFFICE STATIONARY(1 =sufficient, 2 =insufficient, 3 =not available) 1. sufficient 2. insufficient 3. not available	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									
31.	HOW MANY TEACHERS LIVE IN SCHOOL VILLAGE /TOWN <hr style="width:50%; margin-left:auto; margin-right:auto;"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									
32.	AVAILABILITY OF FREE TEXT BOOKS 1. all books available to all students(=1) 2. some books available to all students(=2) 3. some books available to some students(=3) 4. all books available to some students(=4) 5. no books available to any student(=5) 6. no free books (=6)	NO. OF STUDENTS [PRESENT YEAR 2012 - 2013] <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 5px;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align:center;">SUBJECTS/CLASS</th> <th style="text-align:center;">I</th> <th style="text-align:center;">II</th> <th style="text-align:center;">III</th> <th style="text-align:center;">IV</th> <th style="text-align:center;">V</th> <th style="text-align:center;">VI</th> <th style="text-align:center;">VII</th> <th style="text-align:center;">VIII</th> </tr> <tr> <th style="text-align:center;">1</th> <th style="text-align:center;">2</th> <th style="text-align:center;">3</th> <th style="text-align:center;">4</th> <th style="text-align:center;">5</th> <th style="text-align:center;">6</th> <th style="text-align:center;">7</th> <th style="text-align:center;">8</th> <th style="text-align:center;">9</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td style="text-align:center;">HINDI</td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align:center;">MATHS</td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align:center;">ENGLISH</td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align:center;">SCIENCE</td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align:center;">S. STD.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align:center;">EVS.</td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align:center;">TOTAL</td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table>								SUBJECTS/CLASS	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	HINDI									MATHS									ENGLISH									SCIENCE									S. STD.									EVS.									TOTAL									<input type="checkbox"/>
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33.	MULTI GRADE TEACHING IN SCHOOL(1 =yes, 2 =no, 3 =can't say) 1. yes 2. no 3. can't say	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									
34.	METHOD OF MULTI GRADE TEACHING 1. all students and different classes taught by one teacher in one room(=1) 2. classes sit separately and assigned different tasks(=2) 3. more than one class combined and taught together(=3) 4. teacher teaches one class and assign work to other classes(=4) 5. teacher teaches in one class, other classes observed by monitor(=5) 6. teacher teaches in one class and other classes looked after by seniors(=6)	<input type="checkbox"/>																																																																																									

D. (i) ENROLMENT (SOCIAL CATEGORY WISE) [NO. OF STUDENTS at the beginning of session]

YEAR	CATEGORY	GEN			SC			ST			OBC			TOTAL		
		B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	21	22	23
YEAR 2007-08	CLASS I															
	CLASS II															
	CLASS III															
	CLASS IV															
	CLASS V															
	CLASS VI															
	CLASS VII															
	CLASS VIII															
YEAR 2008-09	CLASS I															
	CLASS II															
	CLASS III															
	CLASS IV															
	CLASS V															
	CLASS VI															
	CLASS VII															
	CLASS VIII															
YEAR 2009-10	CLASS I															
	CLASS II															
	CLASS III															
	CLASS IV															
	CLASS V															
	CLASS VI															
	CLASS VII															
	CLASS VIII															

YEAR	CATEGORY	GEN			SC			ST			OBC			TOTAL		
		B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	21	22	23
YEAR 2010-11	CLASS I															
	CLASS II															
	CLASS III															
	CLASS IV															
	CLASS V															
	CLASS VI															
	CLASS VII															
	CLASS VIII															
YEAR 2011-12	CLASS I															
	CLASS II															
	CLASS III															
	CLASS IV															
	CLASS V															
	CLASS VI															
	CLASS VII															
	CLASS VIII															

*NOTE--- B=BOYS and G=GIRLS

D. (ii) DETAILS OF ENROLMENT, ATTENDANCE AND DROPOUT FOR PRESENT YEAR 2012 - 2013

CLASSES	GEN									SC									ST									OBC									TOTAL																							
	TOT. ENRL.			REG.			IREG.			DROP OUT			TOT. ENRL.			REG.			IREG.			DROP OUT			TOT. ENRL.			REG.			IREG.			DROP OUT			TOT. ENRL.			REG.			IREG.			DROP OUT														
	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T	B	G	T						
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61
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NOTE:- regular students: more than 20 days in a month coming to school
 irregular students: more than average days not coming to school
 drop out students: who are not coming to school from more than one month or left the school
 TOT. ENRL. -total enrolment, REG. - regular, IREG. -irregular, B -boys, G -girls, T -total)

COMPARE THE SCHOOL ENROLMENT OF LAST THREE YEARS, IF THE ENROLMENT IS DROPPING THEN ASK PRINCIPAL WHAT MAJOR THREE REASONS OF DROP:-

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

COMMENTS :-

1. SCHOOL _____
2. CLASSROOMS _____
3. TEACHERS _____
4. CHILDREN _____
5. OVER ALL _____
6. ANY OTHER _____

“A BIG THANKS FOR YOUR SUPPORT”